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EDUCATION, A CONSTITUTIONAL AND SOCIAL RIGHT, IN PANDEMIC TIMES - A BRIEF DISCUSSION

AUTHORS

Evaldo Freires de Carvalho (evaldofreires@hotmail.com); Arquimedes Martins Gois

ABSTRACT

The Right to Education is a constitutional and social right, understood as a human right. Brazil has faced educational problems of inequality and equity in access to education for decades. Faced with the context of a pandemic and social isolation, education has become remote, highlighting the difficulties previously faced, making them emerge, which has fostered debates and discussions nationwide, in the three federal, state and municipal spheres. Thus, the study is justified because it is necessary to reflect on the right to education as a constitutional and social right, in times of pandemic, and aims to analyze the right to education in Brazil in the current post-pandemic moment. To this end, bibliographic research was used, carried out in a virtual environment, with articles made available and annals on reliable websites, notebooks and theses with scientific content that, as well as discussions and results, are presented in titles. The author's conclusions and some impressions can be found in the final considerations.